

An Empirical Study on Green Banking Initiatives by Private and Public Sector Banks and Customer's Awareness in Rural India

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Abstract

Reserve Bank of India defines "Green Banking is an umbrella term referring to practices and guidelines that makes banks sustainable in economic, environment and social dimensions. It aims to make banking processes and the use of IT and physical infrastructure as efficient and effective as possible, with zero or minimal impact on the environment". Green banking is paperless banking, which not only reduces the cost of banking activities but also helps in environment sustainability. It was promoting environmental friendly practices and reducing the carbon footprint from banking activities. It helps in reducing the use of paper, power and energy. The prime benefit of the green banking approach is the protection of natural resources and the environment. This study was conducted on green banking which included the banks as well as the customers of the banks to know the various green banking initiatives taken up by the banks and the customer's knowledge on green banking both in public sector and private sector banks in rural India.

Keywords: Green Banking, Environmental Protection, Customers Awareness.

Introduction

Banks play an important role in the development of a nation as well as promoting environmentally sustainable and socially responsible investment. Banks may not be the polluters themselves, but they usually have a banking relationship with some companies or investments or projects that are polluters. Banks can utilize green banking as an opportunity to make the industries grow green and in the process restore the natural environment. This concept of Green Banking will be equally beneficial to the consumers, banks, industries and the economy.

The banking sector is one of the key resources of funding manufacturing venture such as steel, paper, cement, chemicals, fertilizers, power, textiles, etc., which produce the highest carbon release. Therefore, the banking sector can act as a mediator between economic progress and environmental security, for promoting environmentally sustainable and socially responsible arrangement.

Banks need to be more active in communicating the green banking concept and its associated benefits to the consumers. Green banking avoids paper work to the optimum level; less paperwork means less cutting of trees. It focuses on electronic transactions like the use of ATM, mobile banking, online banking, etc. for various banking transactions by the customers. Electronic transaction not only aids towards sustainability but also provides convenience to the customers as well as to the banks. The green banking system would allow the customer to complete the transactions without paperwork. It means to support green practices and to decrease the carbon footprint from banking function.

Review of Literature

Goyal & Joshi (2011)¹ studied social and ethical issues such as social banking, ethical banking, green banking and rural banking which assist the accomplishment of sustainable development of banking. They concluded that banks could perform as a socially and ethically familiarized organization by payment of loan only to those businesses which have green concerns.

Ravi Meena (2013)² covered the various aspects of green banking such as benefits of green banking, methods adopting green banking, initiatives taken by Indian banks and finally make suggestions for banks to encourage green banking.

Sarita Bahl (2012)³ conducted an empirical study on 'Green Banking- The new strategic imperative found that carbon footprint decrease by green building had been given top main concern in green banking strategies and green banking financial products have also been particular importance.

Jaggi Geetika (2014)⁴ evaluated the green banking initiatives taken by SBI ICIC bank. There is an urgent need to create awareness and follow green banking practices to make our environment human-friendly and cover the green banking products, methods, opportunities benefits and challenges of green banking.

Churasia (2014)⁵ found the benefits, deal with challenges and strategic aspects of green banking and position of India banks regarding green banking adoption. He found that there have not been many proposals in this regard by the banks in India. The researcher suggested that the bank should go green and participate optimistic position to find environmental aspects as part of their loan principle.

Nath, Nayak & Goel (2014)⁶ analyzed the green banking practices of top four public and private sector banks in India and conclude that if Indian banks want to penetrate global economy, it is important for them to recognize their responsibilities as a global corporate citizen.

Dr. Nirav R Joshi & Prof. Suraj (2017)⁷, observed that, all over the world, banks and financial institution are concerned about the overall impact of the weakening of the environment. To sustain the development of the Indian economy, bank and financial institution have to work harder as compare to big foreign banks as they are playing an important role in maintaining the sustainability of their country economy. Currently, in India, the concept of green banking is catching up and banks are actively looking for ways to portray themselves as a Green Bank. The banking and financial sectors should be made to work for sustainable development.

Omid Sharifi & Bentolhoda K. Hossein (2015)⁸ made a SWOC analysis of four public sector banks green initiatives. The study concludes that there is a vast range of green banking opportunities for the financial sector.

Sudhalakshmi and Chinnadori (2014)⁹ present the status of Indian Banks in respect of Green Banking and state that though goes green mantra is essential for emerging economies like India, but significant efforts have not been taken. Banks are required to include their green aspect in the lending principle. Every step taken today will mean a better global environment in the future. So a

policy measure to promote Green Banking is needed in India. Indian banks are running behind time in adoption of this green phenomenon. Serious steps are required to be taken in this regard.

Kirakosyan and Danaiata (2014)¹⁰ stated that Indian banks need to make changes in their management practices by way of interaction with their customers and put attention on relationship, communication and innovative banking techniques.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the concept of 'Green Banking'.
2. To identify the steps necessary to adopt Green Banking.
3. To examine and compare the green banking initiatives by public and private sector banks.
4. To find out the customer's awareness of green banking.

Research Methodology

The data collected for this study is mainly based on primary data and remaining on secondary data. Two surveys were conducted; one was in terms of banks perspective and the other in terms of the customer's perspective. It was done to understand the various initiatives taken up by the banks and customer's awareness about green banking. This study is confined to only two public sector banks (State Bank of India & Canara Bank) and two private sector banks (HDFC & Karnataka Bank) of Nelamangala Taluk of Bangalore Rural District.

- Sample Size: 4 banks and 80 customers.
- The technique of sampling used is Random Sampling.
- A questionnaire was asked to fill out personally to the bank Managers and customers.

Steps in Green Banking

Green Infrastructure

Green infrastructure includes IT infrastructure (Data Centers), green buildings with sufficient natural lightening and air, generate electricity for their use and waste recycling plants to recycle their waste. Green infrastructure may also be considered self-service passbook printers, Kiosks, cash deposit machines and contact center, etc. It facilitates to reduce banks internal carbon footprint.

Use of Green Credit Cards

Some of the banks introduced Green Credit Card. The benefit of using a green credit card is that banks will donate funds to an environment-friendly non-profit organization from every rupee you spend on your credit card to a worthwhile cause of environment protection.

Save Paper

A bank should purchase recycled paper products with the highest post-consumer waste content possible. This includes monthly statements, brochures, ATM receipts, annual reports, newsletters, copy paper, envelopes, etc. whenever available, vegetable-based inks are used instead of less environment friendly oil-based inks.

Use of Solar and Wind Energy

Using solar and wind energy is one of the noble cause of going green. State Bank of India (SBI) has become the first bank in the country to venture into the generation of green power by installing windmills for captive use. As part of its green banking initiative, SBI has installed windmills in the states of Tamil Nadu, Maharastra and Gujarat.

Power Savings Equipment

Banks can directly contribute to controlling climate change and an initial step they intend to start a campaign to replace all fused GSL bulbs, in all owned premises offices and residential. Banks can also make a feasibility study to make rain water harvesting mandatory in all the Bank's owned premises.

Green Finance

A bank should finance environment friendly projects and environment friendly products such as solar equipment, recycled furniture, vehicle finance for low carbon emissions vehicles, home finance or green buildings, etc. with giving some concessions in processing fee and concessional rate of interest.

Use Green Checking Accounts

Customers can check their accounts on ATM or special touch screens in the banks. This can be called as green checking of account. Using a green checking account helps the environment by utilizing more online banking services including online bill payment, debit cards and online statements.

Go Online

Online banking includes internet banking, mobile banking, RTGS and NEFT transactions, etc. the function involved is pay bill online, online deposits, fund transfer, account statements, etc. through these banking activities banks are ultimately consume less paper, less energy and less expenditure on natural resources.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Respondent having educational background were targeted and approached for the study. Among 80 respondents 40 were from public sector banks and 40 were from private sector banks. Respondents include both male and female.
2. Out of respondents approached in Public sector bank, SBI 85% were using green banking products but were not aware of the terminology "Green Banking" and remaining 15% were quite aware of the green banking services provided by the bank. From Canara bank, 95% were not aware of the terminology Green Banking and therefore were explained, but they were using green banking products like ATM, online banking, etc. but remaining 5% were aware of the green banking concept.
3. Among Private Sector Banks from HDFC bank, 90% were not aware of the term, but the remaining 10% were aware of the green banking concept. From Karnataka bank, 95% were not aware of the term but the remaining 5% were aware of the green banking concept.

Table 1 Usage of Green Banking Products in Banks and its Awareness among their Customers

S.No	Green Banking Products	Type of Bank	Yes	No
01	Internet banking	Public	58%	42%
		Private	59%	41%
02	Mobile banking	Public	56%	44%
		Private	58%	42%

03	Solar power ATMs	Public	36%	64%
		Private	38%	62%
04	Green Loan	Public	57%	43%
		Private	59%	41%
05	Conducting workshop and seminars on Green Banking	Public	32%	68%
		Private	37%	63%
06	Power saving equipments	Public	45%	55%
		Private	55%	45%

Source: Primary Survey

From the above table, we can see that costumers are not much aware of green initiatives like solar ATMs, the seminar on green banking, energy savings, etc. which are initiated by the banks.

Table 2 Reduction in Operational Costs for Initiating Green Banking

Type of Bank	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree
Public	100%	-
Private	100%	-

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, we can infer that 100% of the banks agree that green banking helps them to reduce their operational costs mainly through less paperwork and sending the statements online.

Table 3 Ways of Promotion of Green Banking Initiatives by Banks

Type of Bank	Door to door information	Cell phone messages	pamphlets	others
Public	5%	65%	18%	12%
Private	8%	67%	20%	5%

Source: Primary Data

When the respondents were asked in what ways the banks promoted green banking services that they were aware of, a majority of the respondents said that they were aware of the green banking services through cell phone messages such as SMS. A very few percentages of people are aware of the green banking services provided by their banks through pamphlets and door to door information and the rest through various means.

The banks were asked whether Green Banking helped them in promoting their banking services. Their replies were as follows.

Table 4 Promotion of Banking Services

Type of Bank	Always	Rarely
Public	100%	-
Private	100%	-

Source: Primary Data

Most of the bank's branches have replied that Green Banking has always helped them to promote the banking services they offer to the public. This was because the delivery of the banking services has always been easy with the help of internet which has enabled the banks to respond to the customer queries at the earliest which in turn has helped them to market their services and products.

Table 5 Obstacles Experienced by Respondents in Availing Green Banking Services

Obstacles	Type of Bank	Difficulty in operate	No difficulty in operate
Data Security and Privacy	Public	72%	28%
	Private	70%	30%
Lack of Education	Public	73%	27%
	Private	71%	29%
Technical Issues	Public	75%	25%
	Private	74%	26%
Traditional approach	Public	20%	80%
	Private	18%	82%
Lack of infrastructure	Public	24%	76%
	Private	22%	78%

Source: Primary Data

According to the above table, the majority of the public sector bank respondents 75% have technical issues. 71% of the respondents of private sector bank respondents favor towards lack of education, while 82% of the respondent have no difficulty in adopting the latest technology and infrastructure.

Suggestions

1. To make Green Banking Unit mandatory for all Banks.
2. To create awareness among businessman about environmental issues and encourage Them for taking environmental friendly practices.
3. Proper training and educational programs by banks for the green initiatives will make Green Banking success.
4. Communicate through the Press.
5. Educate through the bank's internet and public website.
6. Reduce cyber-crimes and ensure the customers regarding safe online banking and card-based transaction.

Conclusion

Both public and private sector banks are actively undertaken green banking practices in rural areas, but there has not been many initiatives taken to create awareness among customers. It was found that the private sector is little ahead in terms of offering online services. After adopting green banking, it was found that banks still depend upon paper for transactions and advertising their products and services for the rural customer.

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